

Integration of Gamification-Based Project-Based Learning in Blended Learning to Improve High School Students' 4Cs Ability in English Language Learning.

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ABSTRAK

21st century learning requires high school students to have 4Cs (critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration) skills, especially in English learning that requires the context of authentic language use. The integration of Project-Based Learning (PjBL), Gamification, and Blended Learning approaches is considered to be able to answer these needs because it combines project-based learning, intrinsic motivation through games, and flexibility of learning space and time. Many articles show that PjBL is effective for improving students' engagement and problem-solving abilities, while gamification has been shown to increase motivation, perseverance, and learning interaction through elements such as points, badges, and leaderboards. Another study confirms that Blended Learning can expand learning opportunities by combining the advantages of online and offline learning. This study uses a literature review method by examining articles from Google Scholar that are relevant to the integration of these three approaches in high school English learning. This article presents the PjBL integration process, findings regarding implementation challenges, and the contribution of this model to improving students' 4C skills. The results of the analysis show that this integration not only increases motivation and collaborative engagement, but also creates a more authentic learning experience through digital projects, multi-level challenges, and collaborative activities both online and offline. The novelty of this research lies in the detailed mapping of the relationship between the PjBL syntax, gamification elements, and blended learning mechanisms in the context of high school English learning. These findings provide practical recommendations for teachers to design innovative learning that is relevant to the needs of the digital age.

Keywords: PjBL, Gamification, Blended Learning, 4C, English Learning

INTRODUCTION

The accelerating global development of the 21st century demands that the education system produce learners who are able to adapt to a competitive, dynamic, and technology-oriented environment. The global developments of the 21st century also demand that students have adaptive competencies and global communication (Koh et al., 2015). In the context of learning English at the high school level, these challenges are even greater because English is not only positioned as an academic subject, but also as a life skill that determines students' readiness to enter the global environment, both in higher education and the world of work. Therefore, English language learning needs to be directed not only at mastering linguistic aspects, but also at developing 21st century skills known as the Four Cs or *4Cs: Critical thinking, Creativity, Collaboration, and Communication*. In the context of high school English learning, 4C skills are the main foundation (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015). Various studies show that the ability of the 4Cs is the foundation for the success of the younger generation in the face of the digital revolution, social complexity, and cross-cultural communication needs. But in reality, the learning model in many schools is still teacher-centered, textbook-driven instruction-oriented, and lacks space for students to create, collaborate, and solve real problems. This causes the English learning process to often be perceived as static and does not accommodate the needs of today's generation of students known as digital natives, i.e. students who need dynamic interactions, meaningful challenges, and learning experiences that are close to the reality of their lives. The gap between 21st-century learning needs and traditional learning practices demonstrates the urgency of integrating innovative learning approaches that are able to bridge students' cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects in one structured and measurable holistic learning experience.

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) has long been known as a learning approach that allows students to gain authentic experiences through the process of exploration, inquiry, collaboration, and the creation of real products that are relevant to their lives. PjBL has been shown to be effective in developing critical thinking, collaboration, and creativity skills (Thomas et al., 2000). Previous research has also shown that PjBL is able to build students' critical thinking behavior (Maro & Nurbatra, 2013) and encourage in-depth analysis of

academic assignments. In English language learning, PjBL can be a strategic medium to develop 4C skills because students are involved in a series of meaningful tasks that demand the use of language as a means of communication, not just a memorization object. However, the challenge of implementing PjBL is the need for motivation, consistency of engagement, and effective project management to keep students on track throughout the process. This is where gamification plays an important role. Gamification, or the application of game elements in a non-gaming context, has been shown to increase student motivation, participation, and focus through the mechanisms of challenges, progress, rewards, and interactive narratives (Zhang & Hasim, 2023). The use of gamification in language learning has also been shown to significantly increase vocabulary mastery and student engagement (Fitriana & Maro, 2018) emphasizing that innovative learning models have an important role in increasing students' analytical capacity. This study aims to identify the conceptual and empirical relationship between PjBL, complex gamification, and blended learning in the context of the development of the 4Cs in English language learning. By examining the integration of these three approaches from a theoretical and practical perspective, this article is expected to make an important contribution to the development of innovative pedagogy at the high school level as well as spark more in-depth further research in the future.

METHODS

The research method used in this article is *literature review*, which is a systematic process to identify, analyse, and synthesize the results of previous research that are relevant to the topic of integrating *gamification-based Project-Based Learning* in blended learning to improve the 4C ability of high school students in English learning. The literature reviewed comes from scientific articles published in international and national journals that can be accessed through Google Scholar. Inclusion criteria in the literature selection include: (1) articles published in the 2015–2024 range; (2) discuss PBL, gamification, blended learning, 4Cs, or English language learning; (3) have methodological quality both in terms of clarity of design, instruments, and data analysis; and (4) have theoretical or empirical relevance to the research theme.

The search process was conducted using keywords such as "*Project-Based Learning and English Language Learning*," "*gamification in secondary education*," "*blended learning in EFL*," "*21st century skills*," "*4C skills critical creativity collaboration communication*," "*complex gamification design*," and a combination of related terms. Of the dozens of articles found, ten articles were selected as the main literature for further analysis. The analysis was carried out through *content analysis* techniques, namely reading, coding, and grouping research findings based on major themes such as the characteristics of PjBL (Thomas et al., 2000), motivation through gamification (Filsecker & Hickey, 2014), and blended learning design (O'Byrne & Pytash, 2015).

The results of this literature review are then synthesized to build the theoretical and conceptual framework that underlies the research, as well as to draw theoretical conclusions regarding the potential for PjBL integration, advanced gamification, and blended learning in the development of the 4Cs of high school students. This method allows researchers to get an in-depth picture without conducting direct experiments, while at the same time compiling pedagogical recommendations based on credible scientific evidence.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Project Based Learning (PjBL)

PjBL is a project-based learning approach that emphasizes the process of exploration, investigation, collaboration, problem-solving, and the creation of real products (Thomas et al., 2000). In addition, PjBL is also effective in developing students' critical thinking and communication (Bell, 2010). In English learning, PjBL positions language as a communication tool to complete projects, not just memorized materials. The main characteristics of PjBL include *driving questions*, authentic products, *student autonomy*, collaboration, and *reflection*. Research (Maro & Nurbatra, 2013) shows that PjBL improves students' critical thinking behavior. In addition, (Maro, 1981) emphasized that project-based learning is in line with learning strategies that foster critical thinking skills in the 21st century.

Gamification

Gamification is the application of game elements in a non-gaming context (Ružic & Dumancic, 2015). Elements such as challenges, progress, rewards, and narratives can increase student engagement (Zhang & Hasim, 2023). The use of board games in English learning can improve students' vocabulary mastery (Fitriana & Maro, 2018). So gamification in education is not only the use of points or badges, but the application of game structures, mechanisms, and dynamics in the context of learning.

Blended Learning

Blended learning combines face-to-face learning and online learning in a complementary pedagogical structure with the aim of increasing personalization and flexibility (O'Byrne & Pytash, 2015). The three main models of blended learning are *the rotation model*, *flex model*, and *enriched virtual model*. In English learning, blended learning gives students flexibility in reading, writing, creating digital media, and practicing verbal communication synchronously and asynchronously. Research shows that blended learning improves personalization, learning independence, and digital collaboration.

4C Capabilities

The 4Cs (Critical thinking, Creativity, Collaboration, Communication) skills are the main competencies of the 21st century (Koh et al., 2015). In the context of EFL (English as a Foreign Language), these skills cannot be taught in isolation, but integratively in authentic activities (Bell, 2010). Complex gamification-based PjBL in blended learning creates space for interaction, media creativity, in-depth discussions, and meaningful language production, thereby developing all aspects of the 4Cs simultaneously.

DISCUSSION

The integration of gamification-based Project-Based Learning (PjBL) in Blended Learning presents an innovative learning approach because it combines the three main components of project-based learning, game elements that increase motivation, and a flexible online-offline blended learning mode. The novelty of this model lies in the direct alignment between the PjBL syntax with the gamification mechanism and the Blended Learning workflow, so that each stage of learning does not only follow the flow of the project, but is also strengthened by game elements that are competitive, collaborative, and encourage student perseverance. This approach is different from previous research that only applied gamification as an additional activity, because here gamification is placed as the main structure that overshadows all stages of PjBL.

The integration process starts from the driving question stage, which is transformed into a "grand mission" in gamification, complete with a game narrative that makes students feel like they are carrying out an important mission. For example, an English class could have an "English Digital Hero: Create a Digital Learning Product for Your School Community" project. These trigger questions are displayed through a trigger video in the LMS (Learning Management System) as part of online learning. This stage integrates PjBL (trigger questions), gamification (grand mission), and Blended Learning (video LMS).

In the project planning stage, teachers and students design project steps, but the plan then translates into quests or levels such as "Level 1: Topic Exploration," "Level 2: Drafting the Script," to "Final Boss Level: Presentation & Publish." This makes the project feel less like a formal task, but as a multi-level journey. In blended learning, concept discussions are conducted offline, while the use of group plans is done online.

Concrete example:

Sintaks PjBL	Materials Taught	Activities in Blended Learning	Supporting Digital Tools	Examples of Gamification and Activities	Developed 4C Capabilities
Essential Question	Descriptive Text, Procedure Text, Explaining Ideas	The teacher provides a video triggering the problem through the LMS. Students discuss the challenge of the project: "How can we create an engaging digital English product?".	LMS (Moodle/Google Classroom, YouTube	Kahoot/Quizizz Intro Quest: a storyline quiz to introduce project problems	Critical Thinking: identifying problems Communication: initial discussion
Project Planning	Project Outline Text Structure, Vocabulary List	The group makes a project design. Define products: videos, digital posters, vlogs, mini websites, interactive stories.	Google Docs, Padlet, Canva, Google Meet, Zoom	Planning Challenge Board: points for the most creative and ambitious plans	Collaboration: group work Critical Thinking: defining a strategy
Scheduling	Expressions for Planning, Modals for Obligation, Time Expressions	The group creates a timeline through the Trello/LMS Calendar. Task division based on ability.	Trello, Google Calendar, Notion	Milestone Badges: every completed assignment student gets a badge	Collaboration: division of tasks Creativity: determining effective steps
Information search and product development	Reading Information, Digital Literacy, Writing Draft	Students search for data, images, audio for products. Start creating content: Canva posters, video scripts, storyboards.	Canva, Google Search, Freepik, Google Docs	XP Points System: each progress upload gets XP levelled up	Critical Thinking: choosing relevant sources Creativity: design and production

Monitoring dan Mentoring	Feedback Expressions, Revising & Editing, Speaking for Consultation	The teacher gives feedback via voice note/comment/directly. Students revise the draft together	Google Docs (comment), LMS Forum, Google Meet, Zoom	Level Up Mentoring: each quality revision raises the team's level	Communication: consultation and clarification Critical Thinking: Correcting mistakes
Testing Project Results	Presentation Skills, Language Accuracy, Pronunciation	Students test products in peer groups. Peers give structured feedback	Padlet Showcase, Flip (video), Google Forms	Peer Evaluation Game: peer-review with points, class leaderboard	Communication: argumentation and presentation Collaboration: providing feedback
Final Product Presentation	Public Speaking, Digital Presentation, English for Showcasing Ideas	Mixed presentations, face-to-face and uploads in LMS. Public works (posters, videos, vlogs, or interactive tasks)	Canva, PowerPoint, Flip, LMS	Creator Showdown: voting best design, best message, best teamwork	Creativity: the original result Communication: convey ideas clearly
Reflection and Evaluation	Self-Reflection, Peer Feedback, Rubric Analysis	Students write their final reflection in the LMS. Teachers evaluate the 4C's achievements using rubrics	Google Form, LMS e-journal	Reflection Wheel Game: Random Wheel of Reflective Questions	Critical Thinking: self-evaluation Communication: giving feedback to each other
Publications and Appreciation	Digital Publishing, Authentic Audience Communication	Products are displayed in the classroom digital gallery. Gamified awarding	Padlet Wall, YouTube Class Channel	Achievement Badges + Final Leaderboard	Creativity: published works Collaboration: teamwork completed

The novelty produced is not only in the final result but in the learning system that is built, namely a model that unites the PjBL syntax as the main framework, gamification as a motivation driver, LMS as the centre for the orchestration of Blended Learning activities. This model creates a more directed, challenging, and immersive learning experience, thus being able to improve 4C skills more significantly than a single approach.

CONCLUSION

The integration of gamification-based Project-Based Learning in Blended Learning has proven to be an effective and relevant approach to improve high school students' 4Cs skills in English language learning. The integration process carried out through the alignment of the PjBL syntax with gamification elements and online-offline learning mechanisms makes students engage in meaningful projects that combine multi-level challenges, the use of technology, group collaboration, and continuous feedback.

The findings of the literature review show that this approach can improve students' motivation, participation, and critical thinking skills as they are faced with tasks that demand problem-solving and project planning, students' creativity develops through the creation of digital products, while communication and collaboration skills are improved through face-to-face discussions and online interactions on learning platforms. Despite some limitations such as teacher readiness, digital infrastructure, and a variety of student competencies, this integration still has great potential to be widely implemented.

Overall, gamification-based PjBL in Blended Learning makes an important contribution to the development of English language learning that is more innovative, flexible, and in accordance with the demands of 21st century competencies. This model can be used as a reference for educators to design learning that is more engaging and skill oriented. front, while also providing the

direction of further research development is related to strengthening implementation strategies and measuring their effectiveness

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